

Business Intelligence - in Modern Marketing

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Devisri, M. "Business Intelligence - in Modern Marketing." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 137-40.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451667>

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Abstract

Over the past decade, business knowledge has done revolutionized. Data exploded and became pregnant. We only obtained entrance to the film. Spreadsheets assuredly took a backseat to actionable and insightful data visualizations and interactive business dashboards. The growth of self-service analytics democratized the data product chain. Marketing intelligence tools draw data from multiple areas together and organize that data into a unified format. This data gives insight into customers and where the data came from, allowing marketers to know where each customer engages. Several tools provide the most effective business intelligence for marketing and sales in the modern era. The function of business intelligence in marketing allows companies to make better, more informed marketing decisions. For the past ten years, the approach to management business in the whole world has changed profoundly, and firms have been able through knowledge and data conversion, and shaping the correct information and knowledge, Business intelligence joins as a critical strategy for any organization to achieve a competitive advantage

Introduction

As a marketer in today's digital memory, your data has nevermore been more valuable. But with an ever-increasing number of channels, vendors, and, spreadsheets, data sources, and other manual tools for accurately measuring campaign results have proven to fall short. Many of the vendors have built their marketing solution with generic business intelligence (BI), but this consumes several time and resources. That is where marketing performance measurement platforms come in; they are something designed for the modern marketing landscape.

Business intelligence is the technology, "the statements and practices of which are employed for the acquisition, integration, analysis, and performance of business data by the goal of promoting better business decision making." 21st century is known as the age of information technology. Thus the ability to use data and information in real-time has become the key to success for any organization. Due to the modern revolution in Internet-related technologies, the amount of data generated every second is enormous.

Business Intelligence (BI), technologies, refers to the tools applications, and practices used to collect, analyze integrate, and present an organization's raw data for the sake of creating an insightful and actionable business message. BI as a system and as a technology-driven process is made up of several related activities, including:

1. Data mining
2. Online analytical processing
3. Querying
4. Reporting

Business intelligence tools measure massive amounts of information to provide essential shrewdness into models that indicate the desires and attitudes of clients. Purchasing teams can capitalize on this information, organizing campaigns that more precisely target the right audience, and gain a better understanding of which actions generate the highest revenue. When business intelligence tools are unified and used by marketers, marketing campaigns are more effective.

Beneficiaries’ of Business Intelligence

- Corporate executives
- Business managers
- Operational workers

Benefits of Business Intelligence For Modern Marketing

- Business intelligence helps the firm for the effective use of data and makes the data into execution. The firm can make strategic decision by using information quickly and accessing information in practical ways.
- Accelerating and improving decision making
- Optimizing internal business processes
- Increasing operational efficiency
- Increasing competitive advantages over business rivals.
- Identifying market trends
- Spotting business problems that need to be connected
- Design better campaigns
- Target the right audience more precisely
- Best results of revenue

Life Cycle of Business Intelligence

Benefits of Business Intelligence for the Business

Develop Market Intelligence

Like enhancing competing knowledge, BI software can be used to obtain market intelligence, and with BI tools data can be analysed in a better way. That involves identifying customer insights, buying patterns, monitoring customer behavior, prophesying market trends. With all this knowledge available from one centrally located source, businesses can be more responsive to the changes in the marketplace. That allows the owners to plan their production place. They can increase their stock production and decrease wastage. If you can use BI effectively and effectively, it can help the firm in various ways to improve market data.

Data Alliance

Data is being stored in various forms and crossed multiple solutions in most businesses. That makes data analysis & reporting challenging and complex. With the business capacity solution, you can reduce the problems that exist with data locked in various software and spreadsheets. BI tools join together all the data present in your workplace in several forms, directly with your existing software solution, the force of real-time data to provide a more robust view of the business.

Effective Business Model

For having all the data, market insights, stats of customer buying habits, competitor market strategy, it is clear that they will work more on making the business model more durable & result oriented. BI helps you to analyze your company's data as well as consider all the outside business information.

Because of the uprising of e-commerce, the BI become so much useful. Today whatever we want, it is only a tick absent. For company owners, this means, they have to be very specific in placing their products, observing market trends, investing in the right place, and assessing their efforts. BI encouraged them to build a much more effective business model rather than just fumbling around for the light in the dark.

Customer Insights

Customer data from CRM, email shopping, social communications campaigns, and website engagements can make tracked in your data management platform. All can move controlled from a unified dashboard, and you can keep a holistic view of your customer and their communications with your business.

That has become very important for any business because customers have started interacting with a company across multiple platforms and Medias. Consumers use their website, social media channels, live chat tools, email. It will be remarkably challenging to address your clients outdoors a consolidated view of their communications. You can only meet your customer's requirements by asking them in a more informative and efficient way. Measuring the data provided by your business intelligence can help to improve consumer commitment not only through your social media and shopping presences but in direct contact with your consumers.

Personalized Sales Approach

For sales and marketing team, it is ever more valuable to learn other business they are trying to work including. As selling individual, you need to learn the different features of a company before pitching them. Their annual turnover, merger information, sales numbers, trading policies, competitors, outsourcing partners, etc. BI will make your sales procedures more composed and efficient. Before throwing any lead or scheduling business meeting, it is always helpful for the sale steam to understand the lead's interest. BI agents can store all the data related to the target

company’s turnover, budget plans, future expansion plans, sales numbers, competitors, and much more. This research can give your sales team more knowledge to analyze and prepare a sales pitch on that basis. Sales cannot happen on predictions; it passes through research & proper presentation. Salespersons use BI & make modifications in their approach to preparing the sales personalized.

The following are the Business Intelligence Trends in 2019

1. Data Quality Management
2. Data Discovery
3. Artificial Intelligence
4. Predictive and Prescriptive Analytics Tools
5. Connected Clouds
6. Data Governance And Trust
7. Security – Digital Ethics And Privacy
8. Growing Importance of the CDO & CAO
9. Collaborative Business Intelligence
10. Consumer Experience

Conclusion

“Business Intelligence vendors look at the opportunities and challenges presented by serving many different customers with their singular platform,” Business intelligence is quite possibly the single point of constancy in the ever-evolving data ecosystem. Regardless of which technologies emerge, and shifts occur, the foundation of data’s overall usage for most firms will almost always be the ability to serve business users. 2018 was a particularly major year for the business intelligence industry. The trends we presented last year will continue to play out through 2019. In 2019, business intelligence strategies will become increasingly customized. Many firms are no longer wondering if data visualizations improve analyses, but what is the best way to tell each data-story. 2019 will be the year of data quality management and data discovery: clean and secure data combined with a simple and powerful presentation. It will also be a year of multi-cloud strategies and artificial intelligence.

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